

PROBLEMS OF ACHIEVING CONSENSUS BASED ON SOCIAL COOPERATION IN ENSURING PUBLIC SAFETY

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Abstract: this article analyzes the problems of reaching a consensus on the basis of social cooperation in ensuring public security, the importance of citizen solidarity and unity in the organization of state and society construction and management at the level of modern requirements, and in this sense, the concept of "social cooperation" acquires a fundamental meaning.

Key words: social partnership, social cooperation, social relations, social conflicts, consensus, social consensus.

In ensuring public security, reaching consensus on the basis of social cooperation, developing the foundations of civil society, building the state and society, and organizing management at the level of modern requirements, citizens' solidarity and unanimity are important. In this sense, the concept of "social cooperation" acquires a fundamental meaning.

In general, the theoretical-methodological analysis of the phenomenon of social cooperation is an urgent issue facing the social sciences today, because this concept is the basis of effective implementation of management or ordering of market relations in any society, but it is theoretically-methodologically little researched.

It is known from history that the state and the law it provides have been manifested as factors that eliminate social contradictions and conflicts, regulate society and bring peace and tranquility.

The history of political views created by mankind - theoretical views on society and man, politics and the state, as well as on the basis of the experience of the development of societies from the first communities to the present day. At the same time, we make sure that this society was formed as the latest product of the civilizations created by mankind. One of the complex processes in the formation of a civil society in modern times is the provision of social concessions and agreements between people. From this point of view, increasing the "directive" and "executive" forces in society through social cooperation is an important sociopolitical process. In particular, the problem of creating and maintaining an order based on social justice in civil society today is related to a number of factors, which occupy a special place in the formation of social cooperation and social partnership, which is considered its component.

One of the European thinkers, the Enlightenment philosopher Jean-Jacques Rousseau justified the necessity of agreement in order to achieve mutual cooperation in the life of society within his concept of "social contract". He developed specific aspects of human freedom and democratization of society in his works "Reflections on Sciences and Arts", "Reflections on the Origin and Causes of Inequality", "New Eloise", "On the Social Contract". According to Rousseau, "during the transition of people from nature to society, property

inequality increased in practice due to the fact that the difference in ownership was closed by proclaiming the equality of all before the law. Despotism now rests on brutality, force and intimidation, as it did in ancient Rome. But "power does not create rights", on the contrary, citizens fully retain their right to oppose the government"[1].

Rousseau justified this right of the people based on the idea of the social contract he promoted: the contract is not between the people and the government, but between all members of the nation. This contract is not a mixture of social atoms or a collection of individuals, but a community of fellow countrymen and patriots. The will of the commonwealths does not combine mechanically or arithmetically, it is not the "will of all", but the common will that expresses the common good of the true commonwealths. This general will is "constant, immutable and transparent at all times"[2]. It embodies the indivisible and inalienable sovereignty of the people, and the government takes executive power from the hands of the people in accordance with the will of the people, and if it violates this will, it deserves to be overthrown by force by the people.

Social status imposes on members of society a number of restrictions unknown in earlier times. But the members of the civil society achieve prosperity and virtues along with these limitations. In a social situation, instinct without responsibility becomes justice, and wild passions become rights and duties. Even the limitation of freedom is the improvement of mental abilities such as thinking and feeling emotions such as goodness and well-being[3].

The German philosopher Immanuel Kant was an active supporter of agreements and concessions in socio-economic relations. According to him, concessions and compromises for the benefit of each other are of great importance in human relations and mutual activities.

It can be seen that social cooperation actually has a wider meaning than simple partnership as a specific idea that unites a particular society. By the new era of history, it was enriched with the social contract factor during the foundation of the legal state concepts by thinkers such as Locke and Jean-Jacques Rousseau. Such an agreement later gained legal meaning on the scale of society as a whole. For example, in the constitution of the United States of America and a number of other countries, the idea of social cooperation based on social agreement has become a clearly expressed idea. Because in such important documents, not only the state and the society, but also the special agreement and cooperation relations between the society and the citizen were recognized.

Now, as for the idea of social partnership, it was only a 20th century form of social partnership, which has historically been formed since the most ancient period of human life and enriched with new values over the centuries. In other words, social partnership was a product of the events that required social partners during the period of industrial development of mankind, representing the contract-based nature of capitalist society.

In general, there are two approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "social partnership", i.e. narrow and broad. In our opinion, it is appropriate to use the concept of "social partnership" in a broad sense, and the concept of "social partnership" in a narrow sense.

In particular, social partnership is interpreted as social labor relations between the state and workers, entrepreneurs, the population or social groups. In this case, social partnership focuses on mutual relations between the employer and the hired worker.

In fact, these concepts are interrelated and cannot exist without each other. But there is a difference between them. As we have seen above, they are concepts of different weights. In

our opinion, the ratio of these concepts can be compared to the ratio of content and form, generality and particularity, whole and part. In this case, the concept of "social cooperation" has content, generality, and the whole character, while "social partnership" is a form, particularity, and part in relation to the first concept. In general, social cooperation is a universal way of working together, which is more effective through social cooperation. Social partnership covers relations within one sphere or branch of society's life, and inter-branch relations in civil society and creates conditions for the development of social cooperation.

The fact that social cooperation is a broad concept compared to social partnership is also reflected in Uzbek language dictionaries. In particular, in the 5th volume of the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" the word "cooperation" is explained as "being a partner in an activity, to unite, to do work equally, as well as to work in mutual dependence" [4], in its 4th volume the word "partnership" is defined as "to be together in some work". given[5]. It is worth mentioning that the concepts of "social partnership" and "social partnership" should be distinguished. The fact is that social partnership means bilateral and multilateral (often bilateral and tripartite) relations of social subjects, institutions, as well as sectors (sectors), while social partnership means joint activities carried out mainly within one sphere (for example, the labor sphere). meant. Therefore, we use all three concepts - "social cooperation", "social partnership" and "social partnership" in the framework of our research. If we consider the core of social relations in society to be a person, then interpersonal relations within the framework of our chosen topic go from simple to complex and take the form of "partnership - partnership - cooperation". Below, we will bring the definition of these concepts from general to specific in accordance with their scope:

Social cooperation is closely related to the main strategic goal of the society, the idea and purpose of development, and is the joint activity of the population and social groups to ensure the development of the country in the direction of the country's fundamental interests.

Social partnership is an important mechanism of social cooperation, which represents the inter-sectoral, inter-sectoral, inter-departmental activities of state bodies, public organizations and business representatives based on social cooperation.

In fact, there are two theoretical approaches to the category of social partnership: a) three-dimensional approach [6]; b) the concept of intersectoral social partnership[7].

In the first approach, the vision of the need to coordinate social and economic policy views and decisions between business, the state, and trade unions is paramount. According to the second approach, the essence of social partnership is the mutual constructive relationship of representatives of the three sectors in any society, i.e. the state, commercial and non-state sectors, in solving socially important problems based on the existing legislation.

Being a supporter of the second approach, we should mention that social partnership envisages not only relations within the network, but also partnership relations between different organizations. It is necessary to take into account not only the interaction of the above-mentioned three links, but also the interaction and relationship of many other aspects and factors that make it up.

So, the analysis of the approach of foreign experts allows us to emphasize that social partnership is a mutually beneficial relationship of three parties, consisting of the state, the employer and the hired workers. But this view does not deny different approaches.

According to A. Malinkin, "social partnership is an ideology and practice that is the basis for a peaceful, non-confrontational means of regulating social relations between groups and

classes in society" [8]. This definition is notable for its relatively generalized nature. After all, social partnership is not connected with specific social institutions and units. It should be noted that in order to clarify the concept of "social cooperation", let's take it in relation to the concept of "reciprocity". In fact, on the basis of cooperation, interdependence lies as a product of mutual goals and interests, needs, views of the parties entering into the relationship. This concept is defined in the encyclopedic dictionary of philosophy as: "the most general law of the existence of the universe, which is the result and occurrence of the universal interaction of all things and events"[9].

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